

FAILURE MECHANISMS IN BONDED PATCH REPAIRED STRUCTURES

Naveen Rastogi¹, B. P. Deepak¹, Som R. Soni¹ and Arvind Nagar²

¹ *AdTech Systems Research, Inc., 1342 North Fairfield Road
Beavercreek, Ohio 45432, USA.*

² *WL/FIBE, 2130 Eighth St., Suite 1, WPAFB, OH 45433, USA.*

SUMMARY: Bonded repair of damaged metallic structures using composite patches is finding an increased application in the enhancement of service life of aging aircraft fleets. In this work, the effect of bonded patch repair on the stress fields in the skin, patch and adhesive is studied. The stress field in the bonded composite patch repaired structure is analyzed using three different analytical techniques. The numerical example studied indicates a significant reduction in the magnitude of stresses in the patch repaired skin in the vicinity of damaged zone which is modeled as a rectangular slit in the skin. Also, the presence of high stress gradients at the material interfaces is found to be the characteristic of the bonded repaired structures, and can lead to debonding and failure of the interfaces.

KEYWORDS: bonded repairs, composite patch, high stress gradients, debonding

INTRODUCTION

The enhancement of service life of aging aircraft fleets is a challenging problem for aircraft designers. This is necessary to maximize the return on the money invested by the aircraft operating agencies, and thus, ensure the cost effectiveness in operation of the aircraft fleets. An aircraft is subjected severe aerodynamic and structural loads during its service life. These include loads due to repeated landing and take-off, maneuvering, ground handling, environmental degradation, corrosion, etc., and can cause severe structural damage. Thus, the aircraft structure undergoes several modifications and repairs during its service life. Frequently, the repair process indirectly has an adverse effect on the service life of the aircraft and in most cases shortens the expected life. The shortening of service life of a repaired aircraft can be the result of an inaccurate assessment of strength prediction of the repaired structure, which in turn could be due to the lack of availability of accurate and validated analytical methodologies for stress analysis of repaired zones. It is evident that an accurate strength prediction of the repaired structure would boost the service life of the aircraft.

Most aircraft repairs require reworking of the damaged skin, putting a doubler or a patch over the damaged area, and joining the patch with either mechanical fasteners or by bonding it to the skin. The latter can employ adhesive bonding, welding or brazing of the patch to the skin. Thus, most repairs can be classified into two categories as (a) mechanical repairs (bolted, riveted, screwed, etc.), and (b) bonded repairs (adhesive bonding, brazing, welding, etc.). Denney [1] listed some of the pros and cons of using bonded and bolted repair techniques for metallic structures using composite patches, and advocated for the case of bonded repairs.

Denney pointed out that the bonded repairs are light-weight, eliminate unnecessary fastener holes in an already weakened and damaged structure, enable load transfer more evenly and over the greater area, thus increasing the fatigue life of the repaired structure. In addition bonded composite repairs can be tailored to conform to complex shapes and contours, and meet the variable stiffness requirements in different directions. All these and many other advantages of composites make them ideal materials for application in repair of the damaged zones in the aircraft structures.

COMPOSITE BONDED REPAIRED STRUCTURES

The stress analysis of structures repaired using composite material patches is a complex problem from the mechanics view point. Figure 1 shows a cracked or damaged metallic skin repaired using a composite material patch. The critical issues need to be addressed are:

1. Stress analysis and strength prediction of the damaged (or cracked) zone before any repair is carried out;
2. Reduction of stresses in the damaged (or cracked) material after the patch repair has been performed;
3. Re-initiation of crack propagation in the damaged zone;
4. The rate of crack growth in the metallic structure after its re-initiation;
5. Debonding of composite patch from the metallic structure;
6. Failure in patch material.

The last issue can be precluded from the analysis by assuming the patch material to be much stronger than the skin material. The first five issues require a concerted effort from the researchers and designers in order to effectively utilize composite materials for repair of damaged metallic structures.

In the past, efforts have been made to address the critical issues listed above, and to develop analytical tools for the stress analysis and fatigue life prediction of bonded patch repaired structures. However, most of the existing work involves one-dimensional, semi-empirical and two-dimensional plane stress/strain analysis of the repaired zones using either closed-form solutions or finite element based methods. For example, Harter [2] presented a computer program AFGROW which is a modification of MODGRO computer program to include patch repair analysis capability. Xiong, et al. [3] developed a PC based design package BONDREP for bonded composite repairs. The design software employs closed-form solution approach based on hard inclusion analogy to perform global stress analysis. The bondline stresses are calculated using the one-dimensional model following Hart-Smith [4]. The BONDREP program performs fracture analysis of centrally cracked plate, and obtains stresses in skin, patch and adhesive. Fogarty and Saff [5] developed PGLUE computer program which performs a quasi-three-dimensional finite element analysis of adhesively bonded patch repairs. The PGLUE program provides the stresses and deflection analysis at various points in the three medium, viz., skin, patch, and adhesive. Rastogi, et al. [6] have developed a PC based, Windows 95TM compatible computer program modules for the stress analysis of bonded joints in composite laminates. Bogdanovich and Rastogi [7] have also developed a *novel* three-dimensional variational analysis (MOSAIC) to accurately predict the stresses in the region of high stress gradients in composite bonded joints. The high stress gradients occur at the skin-adhesive and/or patch-adhesive interfaces. The MOSAIC analytical technique is very versatile, and can be effectively utilized to obtain stress fields in the skin, patch and adhesive and predict strength of the bonded repaired structures.

The analytical tools mentioned above are computationally efficient and are easy to use. However, the accuracy of these methodologies in predicting the structural response after repair is not yet validated extensively. Moreover, in most of the situations some of these approximate methods tend to neglect the effect of interlaminar transverse normal and shear stresses along the interfaces in the bonded repaired zones. These stress components can cause debonding of the patch from the skin, and their effect on failure strength prediction of the repaired composite structures can not be ignored. The objective of this work is to study the effect of bonded patch repair on the distributions of stresses in the skin, patch and adhesive. Of particular interest are the regions of high stress concentration in the skin in the vicinity of the damage and the patch repair. A brief discussion on the initiation of failure in the bonded zones is also presented.

STRESSES IN THE BONDED REPAIRED REGION

The bonded repaired configuration shown in Fig. 1 is a double-sided repair design illustrating the application of patch and adhesive from outside as well as inside the skin. A uniform extension is applied at the ends of the aluminum skin. Due to the symmetry of the repaired configuration and applied loading about the three coordinate axes, only 1/8th portion of the repaired configuration as shown in Fig. 2 need be analyzed. Figure 2 illustrates the following unique features of the composite bonded repaired structures:

1. Variation of material properties in the two orthogonal directions of the structure.
2. Double free-edge effect at the corners of the repaired zones which makes the problem all the more complex to analyze.
3. Presence of damaged skin (or cracks) further complicates the analysis of repairs.
4. Thermal expansion mismatch between composite and metals.

The last feature requires consideration of residual stresses in the mechanical analysis. The first three features make the bonded repair analysis extremely complex, and require a full 3-D analysis to accurately solve the problem. The stress analysis of the bonded repaired configuration shown in Fig. 2 is performed using the following three analytical techniques:

A plane stress finite element solution using PGLUE.

1. A 3-D variational analysis using MOSAIC model assuming cubic Bernstein basis functions for the displacement approximations in the three coordinate directions.
2. A three-dimensional finite element analysis using 27-node brick element of the commercial FE package ABAQUS.

The detailed description on the PGLUE analysis program can be found in Ref. [5]. The details on the MOSAIC model can be found in Refs. [6] and [7]. Further details on the ABAQUS FE package can be obtained from Ref. [8]. There were approximately 4000, 27000, and 98000 degrees of freedom in the analytical models of the bonded repaired configuration (see Fig. 2) for PGLUE, MOSAIC and ABAQUS FE analyses, respectively.

Numerical Example

The analysis of a damaged aluminum plate repaired by using FM300 adhesive and unidirectional graphite/epoxy patch is considered for the numerical example. The damaged region is idealized as a rectangular slit in the skin. Various notations used for the geometrical data for the bonded repaired configurations are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The geometrical and material data used for the purpose of the analyses are given below:

Skin

$L_s = 20.0$ in., $W_s = 10.0$ in., $H_s = 0.25$ in.; $L_c = 0.5$ in., $W_c = 0.25$ in.

$a = L_s/2 = 10.0$ in., $b = W_s/2 = 5.0$ in., $h = 0.38$ in.

$E = 10.7$ Msi, $\nu = 0.25$.

Patch

$L_p = 5.0$ in., $W_p = 2.5$ in., $H_p = 0.25$ in.

$E_1 = 23.86$ Msi, $E_2 = E_3 = 1.426$ Msi, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.9825$ Msi, $G_{23} = 0.5306$ Msi

$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.2402$, $\nu_{23} = 0.3435$.

Adhesive

$L_a = L_p = 5.0$ in., $W_a = W_p = 2.5$ in., $H_a = 0.005$ in.

$E = 0.5$ Msi, $\nu = 0.3$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The stress distributions at various locations in the skin, patch and adhesive are obtained from various analytical models. The stresses obtained are normalized by their respective far-field axial normal stress value σ_0 in the aluminum plate.

Stress Reduction in the Patch Repaired Skin

The stress field in the skin before and after the patch repair is analyzed. The distributions of stresses as obtained from the FE analysis in the vicinity of the rectangular slit (or cutout) region are shown in Figs. 3(a), 3(b) and (4). The MOSAIC analysis also provided essentially the same solution for the problem of unrepaired (i.e., without patch repair) skin subjected to uniform extension. As is shown in Fig. 3(a) the axial normal stress σ_x in the unrepaired skin in the vicinity of the rectangular slit region is about 1.4 times the far field (or applied) stress. As expected the areas of stress concentration in the skin are (i) the location $x/a = 0.025$, $y/b = 0.0$ (refer to Fig. 2) where normal stress σ_y attains a high magnitude which is about 94% of the applied stress value (see Fig. 3(b)), (ii) and the location $x/a = 0.0$, $y/b = 0.025$ (refer to Fig. 2) where normal stress σ_x attains a high magnitude which is about 145% of the applied stress value (see Fig. 4). After the patch repair these stress values in the skin reduce to about 2% and 30%, respectively. Thus, the axial stress component in the skin around the rectangular slit shows a reduction by a factor of about 4.6 after the repair. The normal stress σ_y attains an insignificantly small magnitude in the same region after patch repair. In general there is significant reduction in the axial normal stress component σ_x in the patch repaired skin in the vicinity of rectangular slit region (see Figs. 3(a) and 4). It is evident that the reductions in the stress levels in and around the rectangular slit region (or damaged zone) will significantly increase the strength as well as fatigue life of the skin after the patch repair. The low level of stresses would also help in arresting the further growth of cracks in the vicinity of the rectangular slit area (or damaged zone).

Comparison of Stresses in the Skin, Patch and Adhesive

The stress fields in the skin, patch and the adhesive as obtained from the three analyses at the material interfaces along x -direction at $y/b = 0$ are shown in Figs. 5 and 6(a)-6(f). The PGLUE analysis is based on plane stress assumption and does not predict the transverse normal stress σ_z and transverse shear stress τ_{xz} in the skin and the patch. The MOSAIC and FE analyses predict essentially the same behavior of the stress components. The distribution of normalized shear stress component in the FM300 adhesive as obtained from the three analyses is shown in Fig. 5. The magnitude and distribution of this stress component compares fairly well

among various analyses. The magnitude and distribution of axial stress component σ_x in the skin as predicted by the PGLUE analysis compares well with other the two analyses except in the vicinity of the edge $x/a = 0.25$ where it does not show high stress gradients. Also, as shown in Fig. 6(b) the magnitude and distribution of axial stress component σ_x in the patch as predicted by the PGLUE analysis is substantially different from those obtained by the MOSAIC and FE analyses. It can be seen that the simplified analysis of the complex problem of the bonded repaired structures having sharp material and/or geometrical discontinuities can be highly inaccurate. Not only it may result in inaccurate solution of some stress components but also it tends to neglect the high stress gradients of transverse normal stress component σ_z (see Figs. 6(c) and 6(d)) and transverse shear stress τ_{xz} (see Figs. 6(e) and 6(f)) in the skin and the patch at the material interfaces. The high peel and shear stresses are known to be the primary cause of debonding and cohesive failure in the bonded structures.

Singularity of Stresses at Geometrical Discontinuities and Material Interfaces

The stress distributions obtained from the 3-D analysis tend to show singular behavior at the locations of sharp geometrical discontinuities and material interfaces. The numerical values at these locations do not show convergence with the increased degrees of freedom. Hence, the magnitudes of stresses at these physical locations are always questionable. The singular behavior of stresses manifests itself from the way the bonded repaired structure is mathematically modeled for the purpose of analysis. In real-life structures there are no perfectly sharp corners or perfect material interfaces. However, the high stress gradients at the material interfaces or in the vicinity of discontinuities (see Figs. 3-6) are of practical importance to the designers even if their actual values at the point of singularity are not.

Debonding in the Bonded Region

The distributions of the axial normal stress σ_x , transverse normal stress σ_z and transverse shear stress τ_{xz} in the patch as obtained from the MOSAIC analysis are shown in Figs. 7-9 in the patch region. The surface plots of the significant stress components give a better visualization of the high stress gradients occurring at the patch/adhesive interface. A similar behavior for the stresses in the skin at the skin/adhesive interface is obtained. As is shown in Figs. 7-9 the localized effect of high stress gradients can only be studied from a complete 3-D analysis of the bonded region; particularly the behavior of interlaminar stresses σ_z and τ_{xz} which show a variation in the y -direction as well. It may also be noted that the axial normal stress σ_x attains a significantly high magnitude of about 1.3 times the applied stress value in the patch in the vicinity of the free-edge $x/a = 0.25$ (refer to Fig. 2). In this example the patch material is a unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite having a higher tensile strength in axial direction than the aluminum. However, the combination of high stress gradients of the axial normal stress σ_x , transverse normal stress component σ_z and transverse shear stress τ_{xz} at the material interfaces can cause the debonding of the patch (or the skin) from the adhesive at its interface.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The stress field in the bonded composite patch repaired structures is analyzed using three different analytical techniques. There is a significant reduction in the magnitude of stresses in the skin in the vicinity of rectangular slit region after the patch repair. The reductions in the stress levels in and around the damaged zone will significantly increase the strength as well as fatigue life of the structure after repair. The presence of high stress gradients of transverse

normal stress σ_z and transverse shear stress τ_{xz} is found to be typical of the bonded repaired structures due to the material interfaces and geometrical discontinuities. The high stress gradients can cause debonding and failure in the bonded structures at the skin/adhesive or patch/adhesive interface. Further, the simplified approaches based on plane stress or plane strain assumptions do not seem to represent the stress field in the bonded repaired structures completely, and in some cases provide inaccurate results. Future efforts will focus on validation of other simplified analytical techniques and substantiation of the analytical results of the 3-D solution approaches with experimental observations.

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Fig. 1: Schematic diagram for bonded repair of damaged skin using composite material

Fig. 2: 1/8th configuration of the bonded repaired skin modeled for analysis.

Fig. 3: Distributions of (a) axial normal stress σ_x and (b) transverse normal stress σ_y in the aluminum skin in the rectangular slit region along the y-direction.

Fig. 4: Distributions of axial normal stress σ_x in the skin along the x-direction in the slit region.

Fig. 5: Distribution of shear stress along the x-direction in the adhesive.

Fig. 6: Distributions of the stresses along the x-direction at $y/b = 0$ in the aluminium skins (a), (c), (e) and the graphite/epoxy patch (b), (d), (f).

Fig. 7: Variation of patch normal stress σ_x at the patch/adhesive interface.

Fig. 8: Variation of patch normal stress σ_y at the patch/adhesive interface.

Fig. 9: Variation of patch shear stress τ_{xy} at the patch/adhesive interface.